

Value-Based Education-A Study of Ancient Indian Education System

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Abstract. *Since ancient times, travelers from various regions have visited various parts of India, in pursuit of migration, trade, and invasion. India was a land of resources to them, with its famous Indian culture, capital, religious faiths, belief systems, art, architectural style, academic practices as well as a plethora of natural resources and climatic conditions spreading all over. Absorbing the traits of well-managed, self-confidence and enormous values will assist every individual in earning a remarkable place in society. Education without values is akin to beauty without virtue, which is like a flower without fragrance or a body without a soul.*

Society should recognize that developing one's moral character is just as important as developing one's career. In life, a moral character is an ultimate thing that bridges a person's self-realization. The ancient Indian education system was regarded as a repository of awareness, customs, and practices that directed and inspired humanity. Value-based education helps students by preparing them to face the world with the right values and attitudes. With the help of this process, students' overall personality development is possible. As a result, scholars exposed to a value-based education system develop character, personality, citizenship, and spirituality. In this review article, an attempt has been made to draw attention towards the prevailing value-based education system in ancient India, with the help of a critical literature review by following the PRISM approach. The findings not only suggest but also recommend the value-based education system for inclusion in education policies so that value-based systems can help for holistic development of our future generations and make a peaceful and sustainable society.

Key words: *Ancient Indian Education System, Value-based Education, Human Values.*

Introduction

For affecting change in the globe, education is the most powerful tool.

Concerning the new National Education Policy (NEP) 2020, Nelson Mandela's words make perfect sense. Moral value reforms in NEP after three decades in the education sector are revolutionary to the world for developing strong characters and values, especially at a time when society is experiencing a moral values crisis.

Ancient Indian education was based on values, with the Gurukul system and the world-renowned "Nalanda and Takshashila Universities." The value-based education policy reforms served as the foundation for utilizing knowledge for the benefit of humanity. Knowledgeable individuals such as Sushrut, Aryabhatta, Panini, and Chanakya set examples for the rest of the world in ancient Bharat.

The shift from the 10+2 pattern to the 5+3+3+3+4 pattern has a long-term national impact. After three decades, this decision will result in a significant change in the Indian education system. The new Federal Education Strategy stimulates Indian value-based instruction through comprehensive ecodevelopment of Holistic Teaching, which is focussed on Bharat, The concept of a learning-based civilization, with a focus on knowledge-based education.

Concerning Ancient Indian Value-Based Education

Ancient Indian education was based on values, and it included the Gurukul (a system in which students live and study in the homes of their teachers) and the world-renowned Nalanda and Takshashila Universities (Vidyapeeth). The value-based education policy reforms served as the foundation for utilizing knowledge for the benefit of humanity. In ancient Bharat, knowledgeable personalities such as Sushrut, Aryabhatta, Panini, and Chanakya set examples for the rest of the world— Aarti Sharma (2018) proposed that students should receive value-based education to transform social, intellectual, and political contexts.

The Relationship Between Values and Education

Education is a methodical approach to learning fundamental facts about humanity. And the central idea behind value education is to install important values in students. Value education is essential for assisting everyone in improving and implementing their value systems (Ryan, K., Bohlin, K. E., 1999).

Value Education's Importance in India

Since ancient times, value education has been a top priority in India. The child learned not only reading and archery skills at the Gurukul stage but also the philosophy of life about its impermanence. Because of this perspective, education evolved in India to reach one's awareness in the ultimate as a spark of the divine, and in this approach, the practice of one's responsibility follows conceptual understanding. Students were taught principles such as culture and values, universal values, personal values, societal values, national integration, and character building. (Pala, A.,2011)

Value-Based Education's Goals In today's world

All teaching professionals are outfitted with technological devices and pedagogical practices. They are required to serve to compensate for the increasing demands of the teaching profession. Because of this objective assignment, developing a theory of the interrelationship between NEP and value-based education will be easier (Higher Education Digest, 2020, July 30).

One of the most important tools in shaping a student's personality is value-added education. Every educational institution should consider implementing student-centered classroom instruction based on value principles.

NEP promotes Indian value-based education through the all-inclusive ecodevelopment of Holistic Education, Bharat centric Education, Knowledge-based Society Development, and Emphasis on Knowledge-based Education. Students will be better prepared for college, will have more opportunities to explore their passions and interests, and will learn to study more effectively. Teamwork, resilience, and communication skills are improved. Overall, the NEP appears to be a good deal. (India Today,2020).

Literature Review:

The value-based ancient Indian education system comprised of Gurukuls & world-famous universities namely Takshashila& Nalanda (Patil, V. K., & Patil, K. D., 2021). The ancient Indian mathematicians, scientists, authors, researchers, academicians & medical practitioners developed systems & reforms which laid down the pavement for the growth & development of human society (Patil, V. K., & Patil, K. D., 2021). The personalities like Aryabhatta, Budhayana, Varahamihira, Charaka, Patanjali, Sushruta, Panini, Banabhatta, Kautilya, etc. have astonished the entire world with their respective work in fields of mathematics, medicines, Ayurveda, literature writings, etc. (Patil, V. K., & Patil, K. D., 2021). The value-based ancient Indian education system has enormously helped India over past decades to grow & make its presence felt on the global platform (Singh, R., 2016).

The value-based ancient Indian education system lacked two parameters – soft skills & personality development (Singh, R., 2016). The new education policy must inculcate modules on soft skills & personality development for the overall development of a student in an early phase of his/her education (Singh, R., 2016). The industrialization, urbanization, technological advancements & western world countries' lifestyle are making Indian school-going students forget our value-based ancient Indian education system (Gouda, G. G., & D'Mello, L., 2019). The present Indian education system has failed to inculcate value-based ancient Indian education among school-going students (Gouda, G. G., & D'Mello, L., 2019). The value-based ancient Indian education system has the potential to equip Indian school-going students with moral & absolute values which are important to become a responsible citizens of India (Gouda, G. G., & D'Mello, L., 2019). The ancient Indian education system was value-based (Mandal, B., 2021). The value-based ancient Indian education system has the potential to transform the world socially, intellectually & politically (Mandal, B., 2021). The present teacher's community has to learn the art of blending social, moral & ethical values in their routine teachings to transform the present youth of our country (Mandal, B., 2021). The Indian government should make arrangements for imparting quality training on value-based ancient Indian education for the teaching fraternity of India (Mandal, B., 2021). There is a decline in professional ethics in the Indian education system over the past few decades (Rawat, S., Karkare, S., & Yadav, A., 2015). Being professionally ethical has always been an important concept of the value-based ancient Indian education system (Rawat, S., Karkare, S., & Yadav, A., 2015). There is an urgent need of making the teaching fraternity of our country professionally ethical (Rawat, S., Karkare, S., & Yadav, A., 2015). Some of the major reasons responsible for the decline of professional ethics in the Indian education system are corruption in recruitment of teachers in govt. schools, colleges & universities; nepotism by senior government officials in various departments of elementary, secondary, senior secondary, technical & higher education, political interference in recruitments, duty absenteeism of teachers, etc. (Rawat, S., Karkare, S., & Yadav, A., 2015). The value-based ancient Indian education system was drafted by ancient Rishis & Sages (Meeta M.). The Buddhist Monasteries & Nalanda University were great centers of higher education during the pre-medieval time (Meeta M.). There is a strong need for Indian educationists to update their academic curriculum & blend moral, ethical & absolute values with education & knowledge to make India a super knowledge power & an amicable & holistic place to live & work (Meeta M.). It is education only that brings changes & revolutions in human society (Mandal, J. K., Patra, B., & Mal, S.). The value-based ancient Indian education system emphasized on social, moral, spiritual, intellectual, aesthetic & emotional development of individuals & society as a whole (Mandal, J. K., Patra, B., & Mal, S.). Indian educational authorities & the Indian government needs to re-introduce the value-based ancient Indian education to Indian students & scholars (Mandal, J. K., Patra, B., & Mal, S.). The globalization, industrial revolution & machine-centric civilization has turmoiled values from the Indian education system (Mandal, J. K., Patra, B., & Mal, S.). The ancient Indian education system preached values like karma, satya, dharma, shanti, prema & ahimsa to ancient Indian students & scholars in Gurukuls & Universities of Nalanda, Takshila, Vikramshila & Ujjain (Borah, A. K., 2014). Education is an immaculate tool to discover oneself from within, realize one's potential & strength & lay the foundation for a successful career (Borah, A. K., 2014). The Government of India should manage & control the education system properly & must make provisions where education becomes affordable & accessible to each & every caste & community of India without any discrimination (Borah, A. K., 2014).

Through an examination of Indian scriptures, this paper explains the Indian Heritage of Value-Based Education Administration. Organizational philosophy, leadership, organizational culture, and social responsibility have all been addressed. The paper also provides lessons from our Indian heritage that current educational institutions must learn. India has a long history of educational administration. It was home to some of the most well-known universities, including Nalanda and Takshashila, as well as several Gurukulas that provided education based on human values. Not only was the education value-based, but these institutions were also run in an ideal manner based on the highest ethical and moral standards.

This paper is part of a larger research project that looks at the need for values-based education in today's world. This presentation explores this through the lens of Buddhism's core values. According

to experts, the 21st-century school curriculum does not support the teaching of moral values. However, many commentators fail to recognize the impact of societal influences on children outside of school. These include shifting family dynamics and the rapid, both positive and negative, changes brought about by technology.

India is the world's first and most ancient nation, having advanced on the path of progressive evolution and prosperity, achieving the loftiest pedestal of world Leader (Vishwaguru) for several millennia in every domain of human wisdom. This historic achievement was made possible in large part by India's ancient elementary and higher education systems, which are rooted in our rich socio-cultural, religious, human, and moral values – as evidenced by the gurukul education system, and higher education system that can boast of Taxila and Nalanda Universities, the pride of the ancient world.

This paper explores the vast and rich heritage of Indian philosophy, focusing on the integral value-based philosophy of education of three major figures of modern India: Swami Vivekananda, R. Tagore, and Sri Aurobindo. Finally, the paper demonstrates that Indian sages spoke about ethics and education not from the dominant materialistic utilitarian paradigm, but from another world view that is spiritual and metaphysical, in deep coherence with Western Philosophical Idealism -from Plato to Hegel and Steiner- and in deep coherence with quantum physics and the new holistic paradigm.

Education is a potent and widely disseminated agent of overall development, individual and social transformation. This alone is capable of sustaining culture and civilization. Education should foster the development of an integrated personality and instill values such as patriotism. Encourage a sense of national unity and a healthy appreciation for the rich variety of cultural expressions, as well as a humanistic outlook. Value education, like value itself, is a multifaceted endeavor. The theory and practice of value education address individuals' emotional, rational, and active selves. It assists individuals in resolving or accepting conflicts with others, as well as inputting their beliefs into action.

Education is more than just imparting knowledge in a specific faculty or subject or preparing one to secure jobs or perform well in exams; it is also training in logical thinking that helps future generations adjust to an ever-changing environment. It also entails opening the mind's doors, cleansing the soul, and self-realization. The quality of manpower for societal benefits is heavily influenced by educational quality. This paper compares the ancient and modern educational systems.

India is on its way to becoming a superpower today. Our educational system has made significant contributions to India's development in all areas. Despite the system's shortcomings, the education provided to students in India is of high quality. The strong foundation laid down by our forefathers deserves credit. Many educational reforms have occurred over the years. The evolution of the Indian education system from the ancient period to the present era has been discussed in this study. Before 1947, the improvements in the education system were dictated by the rulers of the time, however, since 1974, the Indian government has made continual attempts to develop the education system to the point where every individual has access to it. Parents and instructors, on the other hand, must make efforts to fully implement the right to education act.

Our educational system has made significant contributions to India's progress in all areas. The sturdy foundation put forth by our forefathers deserves recognition. The ancient period is further subdivided into two parts: the Vedic period and the Buddhist period. The Vedic system of education is the education system that originated in India about 1200 B.C. As the name implies, education was founded on the four Vedas, namely the Rigveda, Samveda, Yajurveda, and Atharvaveda, which are regarded as God's language in human speech. Vedic education's purpose was to "liberate the soul from earthly bonds." The term 'Budha,' borrowed from the ancient Indian languages of Pali and Sanskrit, signifies "one who has woken." At the age of 35, Siddharth Gautam awoke to the true essence of existence, 'Nirwana,' and eventually became the 'Buddha.' Lord Gautam Buddha is the founder of Buddhism, a religion based on Buddha's teachings. From the Vedic age till today, our educational system has seen enormous modifications. From the Middle Ages to 1947, the changes were regulated by the rulers of the time, and therefore education had diverse goals. Since 1947, the Indian government has worked to develop our educational system so that it reaches every citizen (Goyal & Aggarwal, 2015). Higher education in India has progressed through several socio-historical

periods, including ancient, medieval, colonialist, post-independence, and modern. In truth, this voyage of higher education began with an old system of education in the Vedic period, which included two types of educational systems, namely the Brahminical and Buddhist mechanisms of teaching. Based on the above debate, we conclude that higher education in India has been a comprehensive social-economic voyage from traditional to modernism, as symbolized by the ancient times to 2007, which celebrated the 60th birthday of Independent India. Indeed, higher education in ancient India had a splendid form based on Buddhist social ideals and Brahminical Hindu social order (Choudhary, 2008). However, in the ancient Indian education system, a sense of gratitude or thankfulness was practiced as an expression of gestures such as ‘kratajnata ‘ meaning to regard the act of goodness bestowed onto them. On the same line of discussion, the researcher also found from the study that when God Siva blessed Arjuna with divine weapons, the latter folded his hands in the form of ‘anjali’, expressing the gratitude to the former saying that he was ‘anugrhitā’ meaning that he was helped and favored with the kindness of God. Identical references of this type of education system were also found during the events of Ramayana and took place specifically in dialogues between God Rama and Lord Hanumanta, where the former praised the latter for his brave deeds and acts in Lanka. Apart from providing spiritual guidance, the researcher also found that the ancient Indian education system also focused on imparting skills along with various theoretical and practical sciences in the older upnisads. Various schedules of arts, sciences, and skills such as grammar, metrics, philosophy, medicine, tree care, law, statecraft, literature, sculpture, and painting are to name a few as mentioned in the Vedas and the Upanisads (Scharfe, 2002). The highest significance of education in human existence was understood by Ancient India. The ancient thinkers believed that a good society could not exist without educated people. They carefully and thoughtfully developed an educational program aimed at the harmonious development of pupils' minds and bodies. What they envisioned was a highly liberal, all-around education of the highest caliber, geared to educate pupils for a productive existence in which they might enjoy all parts of life. This is essentially a globally applicable educational framework emphasizing the meaning of human life and connectivity at all levels of existence as the foundation of human ideals (Bhatta, 2009). The researcher has found that the ancient Indian education system also boasted of the amicable relationship between the teacher and the pupil. These relations also existed after their life afterward. There was also a continuous follow-up system between teacher and student even after the completion of the formal education, as teacher and student used to visit each other in their places. Each of these visits was also beneficial to each of them. This ensured that the teacher keeps a check on the student's deliverance on what the student had been taught earlier (Altekar, 2009).

Education is a forum through which young generations are schooled and prepared for the future. Education imparts information and skills that enable a person to be employed. Because of its progression from ancient to contemporary education, the Indian education system is widely popular and diverse among other nations' education systems. Teachers instructed pupils in the ancient and medieval ages of education so that they might survive and exist in that time (Ghonge, Bag, & Singh, 2020). This also keeps a check on students' perceptions throughout. The researcher has found that the pupils lacked the idea of perception when it came to matters such as politics, situational dilemmas, and so on. It was discovered that this was due to our modern-day schooling focusing more on producing individuals for employment and less on value systems and critical thinking. The current educational system is having a tough time guaranteeing the necessary quality that every student must possess. This also causes students to be perplexed about their professional prospects and life in general. They are unaware of their full potential and ability, and as a result, they acquire a "follow the herd" mindset (Jain, Choudhary, & Philip, 2021).

Research Methodology

The Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) technique was used in the aforesaid study to sift through various literature sources. This systematic review of literature contained two major extensions: (1) a criterion for selecting what to include in the research and (2) the selection of repositories and sample articles (McLean & 28 Anthony, 2014). The study focused on the many value-based ancient Indian education systems that influence and instill holistic development in children. Reference was concentrated on items with direct connection to current

events, as shown by the criterion provided below. The criteria for article inclusion were adopted, with a focus on the ancient Indian education system for the study of literature through the use of journals from the internet that match the results of the study's keywords, distinct research paper titles on the topic, a review of subjects, and chronological order. Free and open access research papers and publications on the Ancient Indian Education System, Value-based education, and human values with a focus on the value-based education system.

Selection of online articles, keywords, and Database

Google Scholar, one of the most prominent free research resources, was used for the research. It is regarded as one of the most legitimate sources of credible papers on issues and topics in the field of study. Following database selection, advanced research was conducted on Google for the selected key phrases using the specified key words combination while maintaining the phrase 'value-based education' as a constant in all search results. Along with value-based education, other word combinations include the Ancient Indian Education System and human values. The detected papers were then utilized concerning the citations, and the selected 51 articles were double screened using the PRISMA technique, as shown in the figure below. The preceding stages resulted in the selection of 28 papers for study purposes. The screening of each paper resulted in the elimination of 11 duplicate papers. The remaining 40 publications were read and assessed in the next chapter based on their abstract, title, and literature review. Articles were removed from the study during the preceding phase. The researcher's knowledge and the information presented in their abstract led to the exclusion of such. Exclusions based on article titles that match the criteria and their abstract. The Exclusion based on article title (n=4), exclusion based on abstract (n=3), excluded duplicate articles (n=2). Further, 03 more articles were excluded articles according to the researcher's understanding of the people (n=3). Finally, the systematic literature review was conducted for 28 research articles.

Figure 1: PRISMA Approach

Salient Findings

The ancient education system of India was indeed value-based. The value-based ancient Indian education system was drafted by our ancient Rishi, Munis & Sadhus. The value-based ancient Indian

education system followed the Guru-Shishya Pratha in Gurukuls. The universities of Takshila, Nalanda, Ujjain & Vikramashila were world-renowned sources of higher education in ancient times where scholars & students from across the globe used to visit & study value-based education. The ancient Indian Gurukuls & Universities produced highly qualified & competent mathematicians, scientists, authors, researchers, academicians & medical practitioners who conducted exemplary work in their respective domains & set examples in front of the outside world. The ultimate aim of the value-based ancient Indian education system was overall intellectual, ethical, spiritual, emotional, aesthetic, social & moral development of students, scholars & human society. The ancient Indian education system preached & practiced values such as Karma, Dharma, Shanti, Prema, Ahimsa & Satya to Indian students & scholars enabling them to become not only professionally successful people but also generous & kind human beings who can contribute to the welfare of humanity. The present education system of India has become value-less due to corruption, the influence of western countries' lifestyles, globalization, industrialization & machine-centric approach. There is an urgent need to revive our value-based ancient Indian education system & inculcate values in the present education system by the Indian Government & educational authorities. The government of India must make provisions for providing training on values such as Karma, Dharma, Shanti, Prema, Ahimsa & Satya to the educational fraternity as they are the people who will nurture the coming future generations. Also, all possible endeavors must be made by the government of India to make education affordable & accessible to each & every caste & community of India for holistic growth & development as well as making India a super knowledge power in coming times ahead.

Conclusion

Despite the efforts of the government or various Boards, the standard of education in India cannot increase until efforts are made at the grassroots level, i.e., efforts by teachers and parents. We must all work together to ensure that all parents bring their children to school at the proper age and that instructors create enchantment in their classrooms to ensure optimum learning. The education system in ancient India very much focussed on imparting skills, values, sciences, and other useful traits for the development of human life apart from imparting religious teachings. On that note, our present education system may get benefitted from such a prevailing treasure of the education system of ancient India, as it not only ensures to guide human beings to a world of calmness and adore but also a better place for everyone to live in harmony. The researcher also found that insights from the ancient Indian educational system can greatly aid in the development of a creative, ethical, and learning mind, one that is concerned not only with increased 'progress,' but also, and perhaps more crucially, with the inner change of the human consciousness. The study suggests maintaining strong ethical standards by the teacher and students during and post the educational relationship to help foster the process of teaching-learning intact and effective throughout the learners' life. Our educational system must learn from ancient and medieval education systems in terms of practical knowledge application, pupil-teacher connections, student lifestyles in that era, kings' contributions to education, little stress placed on students, and much more. Because the growth of industries and business sectors will be very severe and demanding, our government must offer a system of education that provides pupils with all-around growth, make their long run, and educate them on how to survive in any critical scenario. To ameliorate the situation, a major reform in the educational system is required, and this transformation can only be supported by a return to India's old education system. Instead of focusing just on academics, the emphasis must now shift to skill development. These archaic traditions cannot be used in the present times. As a result, its use needs reinvention and resurrection to assist today's pupils. In today's ever-changing world, where competition is fierce, improving skills is the only way to weather the storm. And this is only achievable if kids are encouraged to acquire these talents from an early age. The British destroyed the ancient school system to undermine our value system and make it easier for them to control us. It is now time to resurrect and reimagine the traditional techniques of providing education to meet our modern-day demands.

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